

NDAC/LO/001

1982 May 3

WP5100:

Set Solution - Definition of Process and I/O Interfaces1. Principles and Terminology

The purpose of the set solution is to reduce all grid coordinates collected in a given time window (~ 12 h duration) onto a given fixed reference great circle (RGC). The set is therefore completely determined by the time window, [TFIRST, TLAST], and the pole of the RGC, (α_r, δ_r) .

This reduction is in principle achieved by eliminating all local perturbations such as the telescope attitude, distortion parameters (including basic angle), and rapid positional variations e.g. by diurnal aberration. The remaining parameters represent a single position per object, expressible with respect to the RGC by two angles, the abscissa (ν) and ordinate (ρ), Fig. 1.

Only the abscissae are however updated by the set solution. This is a useful simplification because the sensitivity to errors in the ordinates is about two orders of magnitude less, thanks to the scanning geometry and the selection of time window and RGC.

Due to the relativeness of observations, the abscissae are furthermore determined only up to an additive constant, the set zero point correction, common to the whole set. The set solution thus yields the angles between objects as viewed from the RGC pole.

2. Summary of I/O Data

The various inputs required from other processes or catalogues, and the outputs produced, are summarized below. More details are given in the Data Interface Descriptions, DID.

DID#	SOURCE	DATA INPUT TO SET SOLUTION
1	Set Solution/Control and Monitoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • initiation parameters (time window, RGC) • <u>a priori</u> distortion parameters
2	Attitude Reconstitution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • attitude angles
3	Location Estimator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • grid coordinates
4	Ephemerides	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • barycentric position and velocity of observer • barycentric positions of the sun, Jupiter, and Saturn • barycentric positions of asteroids (if required)
5	Star Catalogue	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • astrometric parameters and radial velocities
DID#	DESTINATION	DATA OUTPUT FROM SET SOLUTION
6	Set solution/Control and Monitoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>a posteriori</u> distortion parameters
7	Abscissa Catalogue	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • abscissa corrections
8	Attitude Catalogue	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • attitude correction about z axis

3. Method and Basic Equations

The set solution is essentially a least-squares solution of the observation equations

$$\frac{\cos \rho}{\cos \zeta} \left[a \cos \varepsilon - b \sin \varepsilon \right] \Delta u - a \overline{\Delta \omega} - f h_{00} +$$

$$+ \sum_{\substack{k+l=p \\ k, l > 0}} \tilde{\eta}^k \tilde{\zeta}^l (\Delta g_{kl} - f \Delta h_{kl}) = G_{\text{obs}} - G_{\text{cat}} \quad (1)$$

[Annex A, (11.12)], with the following unknowns:

- Δu = abscissa correction (one per object);
 $\overline{\Delta \omega}$ = attitude correction about z axis (one per frame);
 Δg_{kl} = distortion correction common to both FOV's;
 Δh_{kl} = differential distortion correction.

The total number of distortion parameters (including h_{00} , the correction to the nominal basic half-angle) is

$$\text{NPAR} = (p+1)(p+2) - 1 \quad (2)$$

where p is the degree of the distortion polynomials.

Other symbols in Eq (1):

- ρ = mean ordinate of the object;
 $\tilde{\eta}, \tilde{\zeta}$ = approximate (a priori) field coordinates;
 f = field index (-1 for FFOV, +1 for PFOV)
 ε = angle defined in Figure 2;
 a, b = longitudinal and transverse scale values;
 G_{obs} = observed grid coordinate;
 G_{cat} = grid coordinate computed from current values of the astrometric parameters, attitude, distortion, etc.

Remark: The angle ϵ is always numerically less than 10° , but must have correct sign in Eq (1). It may be obtained from

$$\begin{aligned} \cos \rho \cos \zeta \sin \epsilon &= \underline{r}'(\underline{z} \wedge \underline{u}) = \\ &= \sin \delta_r \cos \delta \cos \delta_z \sin(\alpha - \alpha_z) + \\ &+ \sin \delta_z \cos \delta_r \cos \delta \sin(\alpha_r - \alpha) + \\ &+ \sin \delta \cos \delta_z \cos \delta_r \sin(\alpha_z - \alpha_r) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The "scale values" a and b are the partial derivatives of the a priori transformation from (η, ζ, f) to G:

$$a = \frac{\partial G}{\partial \eta} = (\tilde{g}_{10} - f\tilde{h}_{10}) + 2\tilde{\eta}(\tilde{g}_{20} - f\tilde{h}_{20}) + \tilde{\zeta}(\tilde{g}_{11} - f\tilde{h}_{11}) + \dots \quad (4)$$

$$b = \frac{\partial G}{\partial \zeta} = (\tilde{g}_{01} - f\tilde{h}_{01}) + 2\tilde{\zeta}(\tilde{g}_{02} - f\tilde{h}_{02}) + \tilde{\eta}(\tilde{g}_{11} - f\tilde{h}_{11}) + \dots \quad (5)$$

Computation of G_{cat} for extraplanetary objects

Given $\alpha_o, \delta_o, \mu_\alpha \cos \delta_o, \mu_\delta, \tilde{\omega}$, and v_R , the proper direction $\underline{u}$ is obtained according to Eqs (2.3) - (2.9) in Annex A. The correct form of the relativistic tensor $\underline{\Gamma}$ is yet to be defined; for the moment it is perhaps sufficient to put

$$\underline{\Gamma} = \sum_n \underline{\Gamma}_n \quad (6)$$

with

$$\underline{\Gamma}_n = \frac{2GM_n/c^2}{|\underline{\rho}_n| \{ |\underline{\rho}_n| - \underline{\rho}_n \cdot \underline{u} \}} (\underline{\rho}_n \wedge \underline{u}) \wedge \quad (7)$$

representing the effect of the n:th Solar System body ($n = 1, 2, 3, 4$ for the Sun, Earth, Jupiter, and Saturn). Here $\underline{\rho}_n$ are satellitocentric coordinates of the bodies and M_n their masses. Which terms must be included in (6) depends on the satellitocentric angle (θ_n) between the object and respective body, see Table 1.

TABLE 1. Values of $2GM_n/c^2$ according to the IAU (1976) System of Astronomical Constants, and the minimum satellite-centric angle ($\theta_{n,min}$) for gravitational deflexion < 0.1 mas.

n	BODY	$2GM_n/c^2$	$\theta_{n,min}$	REMARK
1	Sun	2953.250032 m	177.2°	-
2	Earth	0.008870 m	47.0°	geostationary altitude
3	Jupiter	2.819139 m	0.9°	-
4	Saturn	0.843944 m	0.14°	-

Remark: Since it is unlikely that any object can be observed within 0.14° from Saturn, the term Γ_4 can safely be neglected. This may be true also for Γ_3 . It is suggested that only Γ_1 and Γ_2 are included for the time being. Thus RJUP(K) and RSAT(K) are not needed as input for the set solution (DID4).

In Eq (2.5) of Annex A,

$$\tau = \text{TMID} - \text{TEPOCH} \quad (8)$$

where TMID is the mid-time of the frame and TEPOCH is the common epoch of the mission to which the positions (α_0, δ_0) refer, and

$$R = 1.49597870 \cdot 10^{11} \text{ m} \quad (9)$$

is the Astronomical Unit [IAU (1976)].

From the object direction $\underline{u} = (\alpha, \delta)$ and the attitude angles ($\alpha_2, \delta_2, \omega$), the field coordinates and field index (η, ζ, f) are obtained as

$$f = \text{sign}[\sin(\omega + \alpha_2 - \frac{1}{2}\pi)] \quad (10)$$

$$\eta = -(\omega + \alpha_2 - \frac{1}{2}\pi) - f \cdot \zeta \quad (11)$$

where $\frac{1}{2}\gamma$ is the nominal basic half-angle. ζ and q_z are defined in Fig. 3.

From (η, ζ, f) we finally have

$$G_{\text{cat}} = -f \tilde{h}_{00} + \sum_{\substack{k+l=p \\ k+l=1 \\ k, l > 0}} \eta^k \zeta^l (\tilde{g}_{k\ell} - f \tilde{h}_{k\ell}) \quad (12)$$

Computation of G_{cat} for planetary objects (asteroids)

The objective of the planetary observations is to measure the instantaneous proper direction along a suitable great circle (which may be the RGC or a better approximation to the instantaneous principal plane). Hence we need not be able, at this stage, to compute $\underline{u}$ rigorously, e.g. including gravitational light bending. The object's ephemeris will in fact merely serve as a reference for calculating O-C's. The algorithm must of course be absolutely well-defined and explicated.

It may then be sufficient to include the effects of planetary aberration (by using the barycentric position RAST at time $\text{TMID} - |\text{RAST} - \text{ROBS}|/c$) and stellar aberration [by means of Eq. (2.8)]. The unit vector $\underline{u}$ is (2.8) is thus obtained simply by normalizing the satellitocentric position $\text{RAST} - \text{ROBS}$. Remaining computations are exactly the same as for extraplanetary objects.

Solution of observation equations

Normal equations are formed from Eq (1) after division by the estimated standard deviation (mean error) of G_{obs} as obtained from the Location Estimator.

The covariance of the a priori distortion parameters is incorporated by adding the inverse of the covariance matrix to the corresponding part of the normal equations.

The abscissa zero point is provisionally fixed by postulating $\Delta u = 0$ for one star; the choice of this is arbitrary except that a well-connected star is preferred, e.g. near one of the scanning nodes.

Due to erroneous a priori positions it will frequently happen that G_{cat} deviates from its true value by more than half a slit period. This slit ambiguity is no problem for the set solution as long as a given star will consistently be wrong by the same integral number of slits; the abscissa solution will then be wrong by a corresponding amount and the slit ambiguity does not show up in the residuals of the solution. A necessary condition for this is however that the slit ambiguity is not, in some frames, absorbed by the frame attitude solution ($\overline{\Delta\omega}$). This might happen if the average a priori error in a frame exceeds half a period. To prevent this it may be necessary to impose a constraint on the variation of $\overline{\Delta\omega}$ from one frame to the next. The automatic procedure for eliminating deviating observations must be able to cope with remaining cases of inconsistent slit ambiguities.

The solution and full covariance of the distortion parameters is output to the Control and Monitoring segment. The frame attitude solutions are output to the Attitude Catalogue. The abscissa corrections with estimated standard deviations are output to the Abscissa Catalogue. Standard deviations may be estimated from the total weight of the grid coordinates of that star or some similar statistic; occasional comparison with mean errors from the inverse normal equations matrix should be possible.

FIGURE 1. Spherical triangle for the definition of u , ρ .

- (α, δ) = object direction (RA, Dec)
 (α_r, δ_r) = position of RGC pole
 $(0, \frac{1}{2}\pi)$ = north equatorial pole
 u = abscissa of object
 ρ = ordinate of object

FIGURE 2. Spherical triangle for the definition of ϵ .
 Note that ϵ must be correctly signed; in this figure $\epsilon > 0$.

- (α, δ) = object direction = $\underline{u}$
- (α_r, δ_r) = position of RGC pole = $\underline{r}$
- (α_z, δ_z) = position of z axis = $\underline{z}$
- ρ = ordinate of object
- ζ = transverse field coordinate

FIGURE 3. Spherical triangle for the definition of ζ and q_z .

- (α, δ) = object direction
 (α_z, δ_z) = position of z axis (two attitude angles)
 $p, \underline{f}$ = positions of field centres (PFOV, FFOV)
 $\underline{x}$ = x axis, bisecting p and $\underline{f}$
 (η, ζ) = field coordinates
 γ = nominal basic angle
 ω = argument of x axis (third attitude angle)

DID 1		OUTPUT FROM : SET SOLUTION / CONTROL AND MONITORING INPUT TO : SET SOLUTION					PAGE : 1 OF 1 DATE : 82.05.05		
DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	MIN	RANGE MAX	DEF	NUM ACC ABS REL	DIG- ITS	
		1. <u>For each set:</u>							
ISET	-	set identification number	-	1	$9 \cdot 10^5$	-	1 -	6	
TFIRST, TLAST	-	time window of set	s	0	$2 \cdot 10^8$	-	10^{-6} -	15	
RAR	α_r (p31)	Right Ascension of RGC pole	rad	$-\pi$	π	-	10^{-11} -	12	
DECR	δ_r (p31)	Declination of RGC pole	rad	$-\frac{1}{2}\pi$	$\frac{1}{2}\pi$	-	10^{-11} -	12	
NPAR	-	number of distortion parameters	-	0	99	0	1 -	2	
PAR(IPAR)	$\tilde{g}_{k\ell}, \tilde{h}_{k\ell}$ (p33)	<u>a priori</u> distortion parameters, IPAR = 1 to NPAR	GPER/rad ^m	-10^{12}	10^{12}	0	- 10^{-8}	8	
CPAR(IPAR, JPAR)	-	covariance of PAR(IPAR), JPAR = IPAR to NPAR	GPER ² /rad ^{2m}	-10^{38}	10^{38}	0	- 10^{-16}	16	

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DID 2		OUTPUT FROM : ATTITUDE RECONSTITUTION INPUT TO : SET SOLUTION					PAGE : 1 OF 1 DATE : 82.05.05		
DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	MIN	RANGE MAX	DEF	NUM ACC ABS REL	DIG- ITS	
		1. <u>For each frame:</u>							
IFRAME	-	frame identification number	-	1	$9 \cdot 10^8$	-	1 -	9	
TMID	t_K (p31)	frame mid-time	s	0	$2 \cdot 10^8$	-	10^{-6} -	15	
RAZ	α_z (p6)	Right Ascension of z axis	rad	$-\pi$	π	-	10^{-11} -	12	
DECZ	δ_z (p6)	Declination of z axis	rad	$-\frac{1}{2}\pi$	$\frac{1}{2}\pi$	-	10^{-9} -	10	
ARGZ	ω (p6)	argument of x axis	rad	$-\pi$	π	-	10^{-11} -	12	

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DID 3		OUTPUT FROM : LOCATION ESTIMATOR INPUT TO : SET SOLUTION					PAGE : 1 OF 2 DATE : 82.05.05		
DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	MIN	RANGE MAX	DEF	NUM ABS	ACC REL	DIG- ITS
		1. <u>For each frame:</u>							
IFRAME	-	frame identification number	-	1	$9 \cdot 10^8$	-	1	-	9
TMID	t_k (p31)	frame mid-time	s	0	$2 \cdot 10^8$	-	10^{-6}	-	15
NSTAR	-	number of objects in frame	-	0	10	0	1	-	2
		1.1. <u>For ISTAR = 1 to NSTAR:</u>							
ID(ISTAR)	-	object identification number (0 = unknown; $> 9 \cdot 10^7$ for asteroids)	-	0	10^8	0	1	-	8
IFIELD(ISTAR)	$(-1)^f$ (p8)	field index (0 = unknown; -1 = FFOV, +1 = PFOV)	-	-1	1	0	1	-	1
ETAA(ISTAR)	$\tilde{\eta}$ (p32)	approximate longitud. field coord.	rad	$-9 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$9 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-	10^{-7}	-	5
ZETAA(ISTAR)	$\tilde{\zeta}$ (p32)	approximate transv. field coord.	rad	$-9 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$9 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-	10^{-7}	-	5
<u>CONTINUED</u>									

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DID 3 A		OUTPUT FROM : LOCATION ESTIMATOR INPUT TO : SET SOLUTION					PAGE : 2 OF 2 DATE : 82.05.05		
DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	MIN	RANGE MAX	DEF	NUM ABS	ACC REL	DIG- ITS
G(ISTAR)	G (p8)	observed grid coordinate	GPER	-2000	2000	-	10^{-5}	-	9
SDG(ISTAR)	-	standard deviation of G(ISTAR)	GPER	0	0.9	-	10^{-5}	-	5
GOPG(ISTAR)	-	goodness of fit	-	-10^{38}	10^{38}	-	-	10^{-6}	6

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DID 4		OUTPUT FROM : EPHEMERIDES INPUT TO : SET SOLUTION					PAGE : 1 OF 1 DATE : 82.06.03		
DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	MIN	RANGE MAX	DEF	NUM ACC ABS REL	DIG- ITS	
		1. <u>For each frame:</u>							
IFRAME	-	frame identification number	-	1	$9 \cdot 10^8$	-	1 -	9	
TMID	t_K (p31)	frame mid-time	s	0	$2 \cdot 10^8$	-	10^{-6} -	15	
VOBS(K), K=1,3	$\hat{v}$ (p5)	velocity of observer (satellite)	m/s	$-4 \cdot 10^4$	$4 \cdot 10^4$	-	10^{-2} -	7	
ROBS(K), K=1,3	$-r_0$ (p5)	barycentric coord. of observer	m	$-2 \cdot 10^{11}$	$2 \cdot 10^{11}$	-	10 -	11	
RSUN(K), K=1,3	-	barycentric coord. of the Sun	m	$-2 \cdot 10^9$	$2 \cdot 10^9$	-	10^5 -	5	
REAR(K), K=1,3	-	barycentric coord. of the Earth	m	$-2 \cdot 10^{11}$	$2 \cdot 10^{11}$	-	10^5 -	7	
		1.1. <u>If frame contains asteroid (ID > $9 \cdot 10^7$):</u>							
IDAST	-	asteroid number = $\text{int}(\frac{\text{ID} - 9 \cdot 10^7}{1000})$	-	1	9000	-	1 -	4	
RAST(K), K=1,3	-	barycentric coord. of asteroid at time TMID - $ RAST - ROBS /c$	m	$-9 \cdot 10^{11}$	$9 \cdot 10^{11}$	-	10 -	11	

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DID 5		OUTPUT FROM : STAR CATALOGUE INPUT TO : SET SOLUTION					PAGE : 1 OF 1 DATE : 82.05.05		
DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	MIN	RANGE MAX	DEF	NUM ACC ABS REL	DIG- ITS	
		1. <u>For each star in set:</u>							
ID	-	object identification number	-	0	$9 \cdot 10^8$	0	1 -	8	
RA δ	α_0 (p4)	Right Ascension at TEPOCH	rad	$-\pi$	π	-	10^{-11} -	12	
DEC δ	δ_0 (p4)	Declination at TEPOCH	rad	$-\frac{1}{2}\pi$	$\frac{1}{2}\pi$	-	10^{-11} -	12	
PMRA	$\mu_\alpha \cos \delta_0$ (p4)	Proper Motion in R.A. at TEPOCH (times $\cos \delta_0$)	rad/s	-10^{-11}	10^{-11}	0	10^{-19} -	9	
PMDEC	μ_δ (p4)	Proper Motion in Dec. at TEPOCH	rad/s	-10^{-11}	10^{-11}	0	10^{-19} -	9	
PX	$\tilde{\omega}$ (p4)	trigonometric parallax	rad	$-5 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$5 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0	10^{-11} -	6	
VR	v_R (p4)	Radial Velocity	m/s	-10^6	10^6	0	1 -	6	

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DID 6		OUTPUT FROM : SET SOLUTION INPUT TO : SET SOLUTION / CONTROL AND MONITORING					PAGE : 1 OF 1 DATE : 82.05.05			
DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	MIN	RANGE MAX	DEF	NUM ACC ABS	REL	DIG- ITS	
		1. <u>For each set:</u>								
ISET	-	set identification number	-	1	$9 \cdot 10^5$	-	1	-	6	
NPAR	-	number of distortion parameters	-	0	99	0	1	-	2	
PARA(IPAR)	$g_{k\ell}, h_{k\ell}$ (p33)	a <u>posteriori</u> distortion parameters IPAR = 1 to NPAR	GPER/rad ^m	-10^{12}	10^{12}	0	1	10^{-8}	8	
C PARA(IPAR, JPAR)	-	covariance of PARA(IPAR), JPAR = IPAR to NPAR	GPER ² /rad ^{2m}	-10^{38}	10^{38}	0	-	10^{-16}	16	

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DID 7		OUTPUT FROM : SET SOLUTION INPUT TO : ABSCISSA CATALOGUE					PAGE : 1 OF 1 DATE : 82.05.05			
DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	MIN	RANGE MAX	DEF	NUM ACC ABS	REL	DIG- ITS	
		1. <u>For each star in set:</u>								
ID	i (p35)	object identification number	-	0	10^8	0	1	-	8	
ISET	j (p35)	set identification number	-	1	$9 \cdot 10^5$	-	1	-	6	
TOBS	$t_o + \tau$ (p4)	effective time of observation	s	0	$2 \cdot 10^8$	-	10^{-6}	-	15	
ORD	ρ_{ji} (p35)	mean ordinate during observation	rad	-0.1	0.1	-	10^{-9}	-	9	
DABSC	Δu_{ji} (p35)	relative abscissa correction	rad	-10^{-4}	10^{-4}	-	10^{-11}	-	8	
SDABSC	σ_{ji} (p37)	standard deviation of DABSC	rad	-10^{-5}	10^{-5}	-	10^{-11}	-	7	
GOFA	-	goodness of fit	-	-10^{38}	10^{38}	-	-	10^{-6}	6	

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DID 8		OUTPUT FROM : SET SOLUTION INPUT TO : ATTITUDE CATALOGUE					PAGE : 1 OF 1 DATE : 82.06.26	
DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	MIN	RANGE MAX	DEF	NUM ACC ABS REL	DIG- ITS
		1. <u>For each frame:</u>						
IFRAME	-	frame identification number	-	1	$9 \cdot 10^8$	-	1 -	9
TMID	t_K (p31)	frame mid-time	s	0	$2 \cdot 10^8$	-	10^{-6} -	15
DARGZ	$\overline{\Delta\omega}$ (p33)	attitude correction about z	rad	-10^{-4}	10^{-4}	-	10^{-11} -	7